

COLLEGE STUDENTS SWIMMING ABILITY AND ACQUIRED SKILLS TOWARDS ENHANCING PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES TOWARDS HEALTH AND FITNESS (PATHFIT 004)

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the college students' swimming ability and acquired skills towards enhancing Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT 004) using the descriptive research method. This study was conducted at the University of La Salette, Inc., College Department located in Santiago City, Isabela. The total population of second-year students was 1,059, but the study population was 283 participants, as determined using Raosoft. According to the result of the study, the swimming ability of the college students was excellent and proficient in acquired skills. The proposed measures to enhance Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness focus on individualized instruction, diverse teaching methods, promote survival skills, build confidence and overcome fear, encourage active learning, and utilize technology. It is recommended that educators utilize diverse teaching strategies, like video demonstrations, and emphasize practical application with real-world scenarios. Encouraging self-assessment and providing constructive feedback are also crucial for survival skill development and confidence building. Teachers should focus on individualized instruction and incorporate multimedia learning, focusing on swimming abilities like floating and kicking techniques, and adopting all-encompassing proposed measures to improve the swimming ability and acquired skills of the college students.

Keywords: *Swimming ability, skills, Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness*

INTRODUCTION

Swimming offers numerous advantages, including serving as a beneficial form of exercise, reducing the likelihood of illness, and minimizing the risk of drowning (Lachocki, 2022; Australian Sports Commission, 2020; Barnsley et al., 2020). Swimming abilities denote the expertise and capability an individual possesses in navigating through water, involving elements such as breath management, flotation, equilibrium, and synchronized body motions for propulsion and safety (Greater Philadelphia YMCA, 2023; Moran, 2021). Essential swimming skills include being able to enter the water and resurface, controlling breathing, floating, turning, and moving to safety in the water and exiting. However, the water environment, the activity, and even what the person is wearing can alter their ability to perform these skills. Basic swimming skills may be adequate to swim a short time and distance in the deep end of a swimming pool, but greater skill and comfort in the water are needed when swimming in a lake, river, or ocean; in cold or rough water; and in waves or current (Water Safety USA, 2024; Misimi et al., 2020).

According to the Australian Sports Commission (2020), swimming is among the most popular sports. There are numerous health, social, psychological, and financial advantages to learning to swim or swimming (Barnsley et al., 2020; Koroğlu & Yiğiter, 2020). Additionally, it gives a child the chance to participate in other water sports (Bullough et al., 2020) and learn life-saving aquatic survival skills (Asher et al., 2020; Moran et al., 2022).

Numerous research projects have shown that swimming positively affects the physical and functional well-being of healthy university students and various other groups (Dorofieieva et al., 2020; Dimitric et al., 2022). Also, Dorofieieva et al. (2020) cited that numerous writers argue that recreational swimming positively affects students' objective health metrics, including the normalization of cardiovascular systems, along with trainees' subjective health; reports of vegetative disorders and psychological-emotional maladaptation decline, while self-assessment of health enhances. Koroğlu and Yiğiter's (2020) study also reinforced these findings with evidence that suggested swimming, from a psychological perspective, reduces mental tension and anxiety caused by routine stress and competition while preventing hostility and anger in daily life. Swimming is a nice way to relax after a tiring day. Contact with water is beneficial and helps relax both the body and mind. The steady rhythm of the stroke, the absorption in the water, and the focus on the technique rapidly become soothing water meditation. Swimming is beneficial to your entire health. Swimming is a great workout for your heart and circulation because you use your entire body, and your heart needs to work harder to pump blood to your arms and legs than it would otherwise (Koroğlu & Yiğiter, 2020; Dorofieieva et al., 2020).

According to a study by Misimi et al. (2020), swimming skills are crucial for preventing drowning and for enhancing and maintaining general fitness. Being able to swim is both a physical and cultural achievement. However, it is further added that a number of obstacles prevented many children and adults from learning to swim, such as thalassophobia, aquaphobia, racial and ethnic traits like hair care, the discomfort of being seen in swimwear, parents whose fear of the water may prevent their children from

learning to swim, drowning, illness, and/or unpleasant experiences (Scales, 2020; Baybay et al., 2023).

Scales (2020) went on to say that almost everyone with aquaphobia experiences a severe reaction when they fear drowning, and that the fear of water may be a physical reaction to the fear of drowning. Having a supportive person by the swimmer's side, helping them learn proper breathing and relaxation techniques, helping them gain confidence, helping them mirror the movements they need to learn, helping them move well in the water, improving their flexibility, and starting with easy tasks before progressively progressing to more challenging ones are all ways to overcome aquaphobia (Rahman et al., 2024; Tsai & Hsu, 2022).

Research Questions

1. What is the swimming ability of the college students?
2. What are the acquired skills of the college students?
3. What measures can be proposed to enhance Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at the University of La Salette, Inc., College Department located in Santiago City, Isabela. The participants of the study were the second year students, specifically those who have Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PathFit 04) for the school year 2025.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Method

The population of the second year students enrolled in Physical Activities Toward Health and Fitness (PathFit004) were the 1,059 which included CAS, CBE, CED, CIT, CMAMP, CONPHM, CEA and COA. The participants were selected typically with swimming class through stratified random sampling and the representative of the population is determined using Raosoft.

PATHFIT 004		
Students	Population	Sample
College of Arts And Sciences	35	9
College of Business Education	141	38
College of Education	86	23
College of Information Technology	33	9
College of Medicine and Allied Medical Programs	181	48
College of Nursing Public Health and Midwifery	259	69
College of Engineering and Architecture	254	68

College of Accountancy	70	19
TOTAL	1,059	283

Based on the table above, the population of this study consisted of 283 2nd year students of the University of La Salette, Inc.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher complied with all the protocols established in the research and by the university's ethics committee. The researcher first submits a research proposal to the Office of Research, Planning, and Development for approval. Once approval was granted, the researcher proceeded to collect the first set of data. However, before data collection, participants were given a letter inviting them to participate in the study. Once the participants agreed to participate, the first phase of the data collection began. The data was collected in the month of May during their swimming class for the academic year 2025. Notably, a designated PE teacher was responsible for the overall administration of the swimming ability tests during data collection and, at the same time, solely responsible for assessing and scoring the swimming ability of the college students. The college students' performances were evaluated using a paper-based coding sheet. These coding sheets were anonymised to ensure complete confidentiality. Prior to the swimming ability test, the college students were given a 2-hour training. This training encompassed an introductory session and discussion led by the swimming trainer, followed by the test and evaluation of real swimming abilities. Afterwards, the data gathered was recorded on master sheets and encoded in a spreadsheet for statistical treatment.

Research Instrument

Basic swimming abilities and skills were employed to evaluate the college students swimming ability levels. The study adapted the Young Men's Christian Association (YMCA) Aquatics (2022) and YMCA of Pierce and Kitsap Counties (2021) for the practical tests consisted of four swimming abilities and four swimming skills using observation form, a coding sheet, and a set of procedures designed to conduct a standardized swimming ability test. The test encompasses a sequence of 3 swimming abilities and 5 acquired swimming skills to be performed.

Swimming Abilities	Procedure
1. Water acclimation and safety	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Observe if the student is comfortable approaching and entering shallow water. 2. Check their response to splashing, water contact, and submerging face/head. 3. Assess ability to float with or without support. 4. Evaluate skill in rolling from front to back.

2. Endurance and overall confidence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitor comfort in the water across multiple strokes. 2. Evaluate student's ability to swim short then longer distances (up to 25 yards). 3. Check self-regulation (resting when needed, staying calm). 4. Observe use of multiple techniques with confidence.
3. Survival skill	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Observe floating and treading water in regular swimwear. 2. Repeat activity with clothing on. 3. Assess balance, calmness, and stamina while clothed. 4. Check if the student can float and swim at least 15 yards with control.

Acquired Swimming Skills	Procedure
1. Breath control and bobbing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ask the student to hold their breath above water. 2. Observe exhalation technique during submersion. 3. Evaluate consistency and rhythm in bobs (submerge and rise). 4. Count the number of successful, controlled bobs (5–10).
2. Egg float	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Help student into the tucked floating position. 2. Observe ability to stay relaxed and balanced in water. 3. Assess buoyancy and duration of floating without assistance. 4. Time the float to see if the student can maintain for 30 seconds.
3. Floating (Front/Star float)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assist the student into a star position on their front. 2. Observe if they keep limbs spread and body relaxed. 3. Monitor floating time and the level of support required. 4. Check for independent float for at least 30 seconds.
4. Floating (Back)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Start with full support, then reduce it. 2. Observe head position (ears in water) and body alignment. 3. Check for relaxation and confidence. 4. Assess if the student can float unassisted for 10 seconds.
5. Kicking technique	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Observe kick motion first on land, then in water (pool edge). 2. Assess coordination, leg movement, and rhythm. 3. Check for propulsion and minimal splash. 4. Evaluate strength, consistency, and technique.

The testing was conducted in a pool that was 14m/23m long and 5 ft. deep, and a constant presence of lifeguards. The students took 4 tests for the swimming ability and 4 teachers' evaluation on the acquired skills per day and testing was completed before the beginning of the practical part of the lessons in the pool in order to avoid the possible effects of learning from the practical part of the activity.

Data Analysis

Data was entered into statistical analysis using SPSS. Descriptive statistical methods were used for the calculation of mean, frequency, and percentage.

1. Mean, frequency, and percentage were used for the swimming ability of college students in terms of water acclimation and safety, endurance, and overall confidence, and survival skills.

The observation and coding is a four-point Likert scale to score their swimming abilities.

Criteria	4 Excellent (3.25 – 4.00)	3 Proficient (2.50 – 3.25)	2 Developing (1.75 – 2.49)	1 Needs Improvement (1.00 – 1.74)
Water Acclimation & Safety	Comfortable in water, fully submerges, floats independently, rolls from front to back with ease.	Mostly comfortable, submerges with some hesitation, floats but may need slight support, rolls with minor difficulty	Hesitant to submerge, needs support to float, struggles with rolling	Fearful of water, avoids submerging, unable to float or roll.
Endurance & Overall Confidence	Swims multiple strokes for 25 yards, demonstrates confidence, and follows safety rules.	Swims at least 15 yards confidently but has minor technique issues.	Swims less than 10 yards, shows hesitation, needs encouragement.	Avoids swimming, lacks confidence, and does not follow safety instructions.
Survival Skills	Floats and swims 10+ yards while wearing clothes, maintains control.	Floats and swims but struggles slightly with balance and endurance.	Attempts but struggles to stay afloat or swim properly.	Unable to float or swim in clothes, panics.

2. Mean, frequency, and percentage were used for the acquired skills of the college students in terms of breath control and bobbing, egg float, floating (front/star float), floating (back), and kicking techniques (dolphin kick).

The observation and coding is a four-point Likert scale to score the acquired swimming skills of the college students.

Criteria	4 Excellent	3 Proficient	2 Developing	1 Needs Improvement
Breath Control & Bobbing	Consistently performs controlled bobs (5–10 times),	Can perform bobs (3–5 times) but may have inconsistent exhalation and rhythm.	Attempts bobs but struggles with breath control, needs reminders to exhale.	Unable to perform bobs, holds breath improperly, panics when submerged.
Floating (Egg float)	Floats independently for at least 30 seconds, maintains relaxed body position.	Floats with minor adjustments or slight assistance.	Floats briefly but struggles with balance, needs constant support.	Unable to float, body remains tense and unstable.
Floating (front/Star float)	Floats independently for at least 10 seconds, maintains relaxed body position.	Floats with minor adjustments or slight assistance.	Floats briefly but struggles with balance, needs constant support.	Unable to float, body remains tense and unstable.
Floating (back)	Floats independently for at least 10 seconds, maintains relaxed body position.	Floats with minor adjustments or slight assistance.	Floats briefly but struggles with balance, needs constant support.	Unable to float, body remains tense and unstable.
Kicking Techniques (Dolphin Kick)	Demonstrates strong, steady kicks with proper form for flutter, frog, and dolphin kicks.	Performs kicks correctly but inconsistently	Kicks with difficulty, lacks coordination, or has weak propulsion.	Unable to perform proper kicks, shows no propulsion.

RESULTS

Part 1. Swimming Ability of the College Students

1.1 Mean Distribution of the Swimming Ability of the College Student

Table 1 presents the mean of the swimming ability of college students in terms of water acclimation and safety, endurance, overall confidence, and survival skills.

Table 1

Mean Distribution of Swimming Ability of the College Students

Swimming Ability	Mean	Interpretation
Water Acclimation and Safety	3.59	Excellent
Endurance and Overall Confidence	3.35	Excellent
Survival Skills	3.20	Proficient
Overall Mean	3.38	Excellent

Table 1 presents the mean distribution of the swimming ability of the college students as excellent in the following: water acclimation and safety (3.59), endurance and overall confidence (3.35), and proficient in only one area: survival skills (3.20). With the overall mean of 3.38, this implies that the college students were excellent at swimming ability.

1.2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Swimming Ability of the College Students

Table 2 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of the swimming ability of the college students in terms of water acclimation and safety, endurance, overall confidence, and survival skills.

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Swimming Ability of the College Students

Category	Swimming Ability of the College Students							
	Excellent		Proficient		Developing		Needs Improvement	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Water Acclimation & Safety	208	73.5	38	13.4	34	12.0	3	1.1
Endurance & Overall Confidence	142	50.2	100	35.3	40	14.1	1	0.4
Survival Skills	127	44.9	103	36.4	35	12.4	18	6.4

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the swimming ability of the college students as excellent on water acclimation and safety (f=208, %=73.5), endurance and overall confidence (f=142, %=50.2), and survival skills (f=127, %=44.9). The table also shows that the students were proficient in survival skills (f=103, %=36.4), endurance and overall confidence (f=100, %=35.3), and water acclimation and safety (f=38, %=13.4). Furthermore, the students swimming ability of the college students were developing on endurance and overall confidence (f=40, %=14.1), survival skills (f=35, %=12.4) and water acclimation and safety (f=34, %=12.0) and needs improvement on survival skills (f=18, %=6.4), water acclimation and safety (f=3, %=11), and endurance and overall confidence (f=1, %=0.4).

Part 2. Acquired Skills of the College Students

2.1 Mean Distribution on Acquired Skills of the College Students

Table 3 presents the mean distribution of acquired skills of the college students in terms of breath control and bobbing, egg float, floating (front/star float), floating (back), and kicking techniques (dolphin kick).

Table 3

Mean Distribution on Acquired Skills of the College Students

Acquired Swimming Skills	Mean	Interpretation
Breath Control and Bobbing	3.63	Excellent
Egg Float	3.02	Proficient
Floating (front/star float)	2.66	Proficient
Floating (back)	2.49	Proficient
Kicking Techniques (dolphin kick)	3.09	Proficient
Overall Mean	2.98	Proficient

As gleaned in Table 3, the mean distribution of the acquired skills of the college students was excellent in one area: breath control and bobbing (3.63). It also illustrates proficiency in the following: kicking techniques (dolphin kick) (3.09), egg float (3.02), floating (front/star float) (2.66), and floating (back) (2.49). With the overall mean of 2.98, this implies that the college students were proficient in acquired skills.

2.2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution on Acquired Skills of the College Students

Table 4 explains the frequency and percentage distribution of acquired skills of the college students in terms of breath control and bobbing, egg float, floating (front/star float), floating (back), and kicking techniques (dolphin kick).

Table 4

Frequency and Percentage Distribution on Acquired Skills of the College Students

Category	Swimming Ability of the College Students							
	Excellent		Proficient		Developing		Needs Improvement	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Breath Control & Bobbing	211	74.6	40	14.1	30	10.6	2	0.7
Egg float	142	50.2	49	17.3	49	17.3	43	15.2
Floating (front/Star float)	92	32.5	66	23.3	61	21.6	64	22.6
Floating (back)	85	30	51	18	64	22.6	83	29.3
Kicking Techniques	116	41	112	39.6	20	7.1	35	12.4

Table 4 demonstrates the frequency and percentage distribution on acquired swimming skills of the college students as excellent on breath control and bobbing (f=211, 74.6), kicking techniques (f=116, %=41.0), egg float (f=142, %50.0), floating (front/star float) (f=92, %=32.5) and floating (back) (f=85, %=30.0). It also reveals that the students were proficient in kicking techniques (f=112, %=39.6), floating (front/star floating) (f=66, %=23.3), floating (f=51, %=18.0), egg float (f=49, %=17.3), breath control, and bobbing (f=40, %=14.1). Moreover, the students were developing on floating (f=64, %22.6), floating (front/star float (f=61, %=21.6), egg float (f=49, %17.3), breath control and bobbing (f=30, %10.6), kicking techniques (f=20, %=7.1). On the other hand, students need improvement on floating (f=83, %=29.3), floating (front/star float) (f=64, %22.6), egg float (f=43, %12.4), kicking Techniques (f=35, %=12.4), and breath control and bobbing (f=2, %7).

Part 3. Proposed Measures to Enhance Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT)

Measures to Enhance Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT)

Program Rationale

The findings of the study revealed that, in general, the majority of the swimming ability of the college students was excellent (3.38) and proficient in the skills they acquired (2.98).

The proposed measures are a crucial tool to improve the college students' swimming ability and skills, and were designed based on the swimming ability and skills that need Improvement.

Component	Objective	Strategy (Key Activities)	Human Resources & Budget	Success Indicators	Timeline
Individualized Instruction	To facilitate personalized and accelerated skill development by tailoring the pace, techniques, and goals to the unique needs and learning style of each students.	Provide customized assistance and materials to meet personal requirements and learning preferences.	-Physical Education Instructor and PATHFIT 004 students Budget: 1,000 (Materials for training suit)	-Demonstrate proficiency in without fear or anxiety. -The students' shows improvement in executing specific strokes (e.g., freestyle, backstroke) and leg kicks, often with greater coordination and less body drag. -The students' movements become more ordered and harmonized, reflecting an ability to control their body in the water.	-2 weeks
Diverse Teaching Methods	To ensure every learner can overcome obstacles, develop essential skills, and achieve full participation in aquatic activities in a comfortable and equitable environment. -Diverse	-Integrate diverse instructional methods in addition to conventional lectures. This involves employing video demonstrations, situational examples, and engaging exercises to	-Physical Education Instructor and PATHFIT 004 students	- Showing increased confidence and comfort in the water, higher student motivation and engagement, and the development of persistence and enthusiasm for swimming.	-2 weeks

	methods cater to varied learning styles and prior experiences, enhancing skill acquisition and fostering confidence through comprehensive aquatic education	accommodate various learning styles			
Promote Survival Skills	-To cultivate confidence and self-efficacy in water, foster positive safety behaviors, and ensure students can engage in water-based recreation safely.	Intensify knowledge on survival skills in the curriculum.	-Physical Education Instructors and PathFit 004 students	- Developed toughness by consistently facing and overcoming water survival challenges. -Mastering techniques on survival skills can significantly increase a person's chances of survival in unexpected situations in the water.	-2 weeks
Build Confidence and Overcome Fear	-To develop college students' comfort, security, and competence in the water by teaching fundamental swimming skills	-Create a safe and positive environment, gradually introduce water-familiarization activities with playful methods, set achievable goals to build a sense of accomplishment, provide consistent positive reinforcement, and teach relaxation and breathing	-Physical Education Instructor and PATHFIT 004 students Budget: 1,000 (Materials for training suit)	-Lessening the focus on potential dangers and showing a decreased emotional reaction to water-related situations.	-2 weeks

		techniques through imagery and gradual desensitization.			
Encourage Active Learning	To improve involvement and encourage a greater comprehension of swimming skills like survival skills, and endurance and overall confidence.	Encourage involvement in swimming by means of drills, games, and group activities.	- Physical Education Instructor and PATHFIT 004 students Budget: 1,000 (Materials for training suit)	Improved technical skills, increased confidence and self-efficacy in the water, enhanced water safety and competence, consistent attendance and practice, and a positive emotional response	-2 weeks
Utilize Technology	To improve overall learning by making lessons more engaging, personalized, and accessible	Consider using technology like video analysis to provide personalized feedback and enhance swimming abilities development.	-Physical Education Instructor and PATHFIT 004 students	-Performance improvements (faster pace, greater distance, better efficiency) and reduced psychological barriers (like fear of water).	-2 weeks

DISCUSSION

I. The Swimming Ability of the College Students

Schools typically adopt the swimming ability indicators established by the Department of Education as the criteria for assessing the swimming ability of students. From the present research, the statistical analysis results from the 283 participants showed that the swimming ability of the college students was excellent in breath control and bobbing, and water acclimation and safety. Furthermore, the college students were also proficient in the following swimming abilities, such as survival skills, endurance, and overall confidence. However, it is confirmed that, in general, the swimming ability of the college students was excellent. Furthermore, an international research study investigated a self-estimated questionnaire survey, which revealed that, according to

Moran (2021), most of the respondents reported their swimming ability as good. According to the study of Dimitric et al. (2022), both male and female students have a high precision in their swimming ability. Moreover, according to the study of Moran et al. (2022), the swimming and survival skill levels of the selected cohort were high. This implies that college students achieve swimming excellence through consistent practice and training, which builds technical skills, endurance, and confidence. This consistent effort is often driven by a combination of intrinsic factors like improved mental health, increased water confidence, and a high level of exercise self-efficacy, and extrinsic factors such as participation in swim teams, which fosters teamwork and a desire to compete and improve.

II. The Acquired Skills of the College Students

The acquired skills of the college students were excellent on egg float, while proficient on floating (front/Star float, floating (back), and kicking techniques (Dolphin Kick). It can be summarized that the college students were proficient in acquired skills. Furthermore, the study of Tsai and Hsu (2022) showed that college students had sound basic swimming skills, indicating that academic schools in Taiwan have achieved excellent teaching results for swimming and water sports, and that Taiwan's government policies have helped its people to develop basic water sports and self-rescue skills. Moreover, the majority of students admitted that they had trouble doing different swimming strokes, which they attributed to things like poor breathing skills and a lack of prior swimming experience. While some students were able to complete some strokes, others had difficulty. Notably, individuals who gave a positive assessment of their abilities had mastered swimming since they were little (Baybay et al., 2023). Additionally, the majority of the SwimSafe graduates were able to swim for 25 m and could demonstrate both swimming and floating/treading skills (Rahman et al., 2024). This implies that college students who are proficient in swimming likely acquired those skills through a combination of factors, including early exposure, regular practice, and potentially formal instruction. Factors like prior experience, positive attitudes towards swimming, and a desire to improve their skills also contribute to proficiency.

III. Proposed Measures to Enhance Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT)

The proposed measures to enhance physical activities towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT) were individualized instruction, diverse teaching methods, promote survival skills, build confidence and overcome fear, encourage active learning, and utilize technology.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the results of the questionnaire:

The majority of the college students were excellent at swimming.
The majority of the college students were proficient in the skills they acquired.

The proposed measures to improve the Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness focus on individualized instruction, diverse teaching methods, promoting survival skills, building confidence and overcoming fear, encouraging active learning, and utilizing technology.

Recommendations

In light of the results from this research, the subsequent suggestions are presented:

1. To effectively teach swimming skills to college students, educators utilize diverse teaching strategies like video demonstrations and emphasize practical application with real-world scenarios. Encouraging self-assessment and providing constructive feedback are also crucial for survival skill development and confidence building.

2. To enhance college students' swimming abilities, teachers should focus on individualized instruction and incorporate multimedia learning, focusing on swimming abilities like floating and kicking techniques.

3. Adopting all-encompassing proposed measures to improve the swimming ability and acquired skills of the college students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before undertaking the study, it started by asking permission from the school head. A letter was addressed to the school heads requesting that the research study be conducted for the students. The researcher conducted the study in accordance with the ethics, good behavior, and school standards. The researcher gave the consent form to the participants and thoroughly explained it to them once all required consents had been obtained. The researcher took into account all ethical guidelines, which include protecting confidentiality, maintaining data privacy, and not using any personally identifiable information. The study's participants voluntarily participated and were provided with all the information necessary to make an informed decision about their involvement. By maintaining the confidentiality of the information, there will be no participants' names. Participants were guaranteed that any information they provided would be used solely for the purposes specified in the study objectives and that their approval would be sought before their information was shared for any other purpose.

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